

Social Work Education in the Development Paradigm

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Abstract:

This paper is an overview of change in approach of social work education models in the contemporary society. It focused on significance of indigenisation in social work theory and practice. It helps to understand social work education and its practice under the development paradigm.

Key Words: *Indigenisation, Social Work Education, Contemporary Social Work Practice*

Introduction

The objective of development is to create an enabling environment for people to enjoy long, healthy and creative lives (UNDP, 1990). Development is about improving the quality of people's lives or enhancing human wellbeing. The development context of India in the present era has bad indicators. It is alarming that India rank 130th among 189 countries in 2018. In a fast growing economy like India, there is very limited visible change in 'social progress index'. Social issues and problems raise concerns. Hence, the human development approach is significant to social work practice and education (Mutatkar R., 2016).

New Models of Social Work Education

Nanavati M.C. critically explored innovative and emerging models of SWE in Asia. SWE has Western philosophy for its theoretical premise. The author has suggested 'new models of social work education'. Professional education has five basic components: Context, Purpose, Structure, Content and Process. Co-relation and integration of these components in a process is called curriculum development. Contemporary social, cultural and economic contexts are explored in the social work curriculum. Theories of social development and social change have their basic premise in the objectives of SWE.

The point of contradiction in SWE is related to personal and social development. Professional social workers envision an egalitarian society where roles of individual or professional growth are scrutinized. Today's industrialised civilisation has impact on SWE and practice. Professional social work intervenes in issues of the development paradigm. It can be understood in relation to illiteracy, industrialisation, social security and universal employment. These challenges need to be addressed through application of indigenised knowledge (Balkrishna, 2012).

Indigenised knowledge is considered as a base for resolving the challenges in setting an alternative model of social work practice. The discourse on indigenisation has been carried forward since its emergence. Unfortunately, its academic and practical applicability could not be achieved in India and Third World countries. Causes of failure in indigenising are explained below.

1. Elite middle class intellectuals could not find their roots in the ground reality. These elite intellectuals were influenced by Western philosophy.
2. The traditional approach had a fundamentalist identity. On the contrary, liberal perspectives were acclaimed and widely accepted. Hence, the role of indigenisation has its own limits.
3. The emotional unrest in societies demands an alternate model of social work education, where intellectual thoughts combine with emotional urge.
4. The elitist intellectuals and their Western conditioning did not promote indigenisation. There is failure in balancing the influence of actual roots and the concepts/theories of

the great masters.

The discourse on indigenisation existed generally in social sciences and particularly in sociology and anthropology. National and regional milieus are basic reasons behind the call to change and bring an alternative model.

Contemporary Understanding of Social Work Education

Bodhi, author and social scientist, compels us to think about the professional and intellectual crisis in social work education. He helps us understand the eventual establishment and growth of the profession in India. The evolution of the social work profession in India and discourses on it are the crux of the writing. He raises the issue of synthesising an indigenous theory of social work education and strongly proposed the theory of ‘Dalit-centered social work’ and ‘Tribe-centered social work’. He negates the traditional method of social work and tries to focus on ‘Indigenous liberatory social work’. Bodhi portrays the picture of social work education’s journey in India from its conception to its current discourses. He talks about the anti-oppression social work practice and structural social work in India (Bodhi, 2011).

Contemporary social work practice is trapped in tradition, and inadequate education and practice. The assertion for radical change and restructuring of social work education in India is strongly put forth by the author. The issues and challenges of the profession are discussed in the process of problematisation. The modern Indian authors and practitioners of social work education point out the need for a shift in the methodological discourse on social work education and practice. They significantly raise questions against the remedial approach and try to draw attention to issues of public concern, such as poverty. In the present context, social workers with a critical approach and new theories and models of social change are emerging over conservative traditional social workers. The ‘emancipatory and liberatory’ approach of social work practitioners and educators is strongly set forth in structural social work practice. Strong critics of social work education highlight the irrelevance of traditional social work education and methods of practice.

Conclusion

Signature pedagogy is a field reflection with conceptualisation of social problems. It seeks to integrate theory and practice with exhaustive review of the planning process and interactions with students. The fieldwork activities and programmes in accordance with fieldwork calendars provide a platform to explore reflective learning. Feedback of students’ performance helps understand pedagogy for its future course. Rapport of students with the fieldwork instructor is significant in the learning process. The instructor always tries to encourage students for application of theories to practice. Hence, he/she must have specific skills, knowledge and attitude to engage with students and the community in fieldwork McSweeney, F. (2016). Fieldwork practice has the vision to give a platform to students for application of theoretical knowledge to practical experiments with up gradation in their social skills, practical knowledge and scientific temper.

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